

Global Value Chains Decomposition Analysis on The Sri Lankan Economy

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Introduction

Sri Lanka is currently dealing with major crisis. Sri Lanka lacks foreign reserves for foreign payments [1,2], due to that reason downgraded Sri Lanka from credit rating agencies [3–5]. In addition, another crisis has struck Sri Lanka. That was the proposal of the European Parliament to withdraw Sri Lanka's GSP+ benefit temporarily. According to Withanawasam and Kumara (2013) [6] this has a significant impact on Sri Lanka since the EU is the second-largest economic partner in Sri Lanka after China, absorbing Sri Lanka's 22.4 per cent of exports by 2020 [7]. Due to the fact that GSP is a non-reciprocal preferential trade agreement, Sri Lankan exporters prefer to take advantage of tariff or non-tariff benefits on both their products and services [7]

ABSTRACT

There has been a lot of upheaval in Sri Lanka recently. With the need to import so many items, export income is insufficient to cover Sri Lanka's import expenses. Therefore, decomposition Analysis in export must be implemented in conjunction with the global value chain. As a result, the primary goal of this paper is to investigate and quantify the impact of the Global Value Chain on the Sri Lankan economy. Thus, the following specific goals are expected to be met: comparing the Revealed Comparative Advantage indices of traditional and new trade approaches in Sri Lankan industries to determine a more efficient estimation of export success in the global value chain, assessing the upstreamness and average production length of Sri Lankan sectors to improve production efficiency, and investigating the This paper presents descriptive information about the industries using an analysis of the Asian Development Bank MIRO database. It covers the years 2000, 2007, and 2019. The main findings of this paper are that, compared to 2000, Primary Sectors have shifted to low-technology manufacturing in terms of domestic value-added (DVA). Furthermore, this is a turning point in the Sri Lankan economy because the country is transitioning from primary to low technology. Therefore, Sri Lanka must provide medium to high-technology manufacturing to satisfy the global value chain requirements.

Keywords: GLOBAL VALUE CHAIN, SRI LANKA, DECOMPOSITION ANALYSIS, ADB MIRO

Figure 01: Sri Lanka External Sector Performance

Source: Compiled by the author using ADB Key Indicators for Asia and the Pacific 2020 database <https://kidb.adb.org/>

According to Figure 1 scientifically sound what is happening now to external health in Sri Lanka? Foreign debt increased in 2019 by \$52,626.03 in millions of dollars. In addition, exports have recorded a deficit of US\$5147.66 in export and services accounts, which is less than imports. In addition, FDI and International Reserves are not economically well shaped. But the exchange rate is down/ depreciated from the US dollar. Therefore, no specific sequences were identified in the Sri Lankan export analysis as a result of these domestic and foreign value-added. Following questions may have arisen because of this. Does Sri Lanka export goods and services with both domestic and foreign value-added (DVA and FVA)?

Following that, does Sri Lanka export these exports based on its comparative advantage? Or, more specifically, have Sri Lankan exports resulted in increased production efficiency?

Hence, the main objective of this paper is to examine to measure decomposition analysis of impact of the Global Value Chain's on Sri Lankan Economy.

The following specific objectives are expected to be achieved:

- To compare the Revealed Comparative Advantage indices of traditional and new trade approaches in Sri Lankan industries to determine a more efficient estimation of export success in the global value chain.

- To assess the upstreamness and average production length of Sri Lankan sectors to improve production efficiency.
- To investigate the influence of the Global Value Chain on the Sectoral percentage Changes in Sri Lanka.
- Based on the above empirical findings, recognize policy recommendations that improve the global value chain (GVC) on the economic export-led growth strategy nexus in Sri Lanka.

The article is organized as follows: the second section contains a literature review, the third section covers methodology, the fourth section covers findings and analysis, and the final section contains the conclusion and recommendations.

Materials and methods

Gross Export Accounting

This section provides an overview of the literature related to Gross Export Accounting. This study needs to measure the global value chain. So, gross exports should be recorded mathematically. So, first subsection presents all the research study concepts, then subsection presents leontief decomposition, and after that subsection presents international product sharing, finally, section offers the identified comparative advantage (RCA), and new revealed comparative advantage (NRCA).

Concepts

Value Added - According to [UNCTAD \(2013\)](#) [10] the world trade in goods and services, which today stands at more than \$ 20 trillion, mainly involves double counting. Raw materials mined in one nation can be exported first to the following nation for processing, then exported again to a production factory in a third nation, which can then export it to a fourth nation for final consumption. The cost of raw materials is counted only once as a contribution to GDP in the source country but is counted several times in world exports. Value-added trade statistics aim to identify double counting in gross trade and where value is created in global value chains (see Figure 2.5) These cross-border production chains, which may include only two countries, a region or a global network, are regularly mentioned as global value chains (GVCs). A typical GVC producing some final product for final consumption will include activities in several sectors and industries, from extractive or primary industries to manufacturing and value-added services included in the chain.

Figure 02: Value added trade – how it works

Source: Adopted from [9] *Global Value Chains and Development*, United Nations Conference on Trade and Development [9].

Figure 2 explains the basic theory of value-added transactions, assuming that the value chain has four stages, including raw material extraction, processing, manufacturing, final demand, and four participating countries (countries A to D). Explain. As shown in Figure 2, Country A extracts \$ 2 worth of raw material and exports it to Country B. As a result, Country B adds \$ 24 to value during processing. Country B can then export an additional \$ 26 production, including a double calculation from Country A (\$ 2) to Country C. Regarding the manufacturing process, Country C creates an added value of \$ 46 and can export \$ 72. , This includes a double count from both Country A (\$ 2) and Country B (\$ 24) to Country D. In this scenario, the \$ 72 amount is the final demand for Country D. Costs have been added based on this basic concept of trade. As mentioned above, the traditional trade approach concludes that the total amount of world exports is \$ 100 (total of \$ 2, \$ 26, and \$ 72 from total exports from Country A to Country C, respectively). However, when measured this way, the formula also includes a double-count total of \$ 28, which can be misleading. Therefore, the sum of US \$ 72 domestic value exports (\$ 2, 24, and \$ 46 from domestic value exports from Country A to Country C, respectively) is used as a new approach to measure the value of exports. It can provide a more accurate measurement of export value and reduce misleading problems.

Vertical specialization - In a globalized world, the global trade model is transforming into a vertical specialization (VS) chain that can increase the volume of global trade. According to [Hummels et al 2001 \[11\]](#) an essential idea of verticality of trade is that countries, in turn, link up with each other to produce final goods. There are probably many approaches to characterizing this relationship, but they focus on three conditions that they believe cover the main aspects of serial communication.

“Vertical specialization occurs when: [11]

A good is produced in two or more sequential stages,

1. Two or more countries provide value-added during the production of the good,
2. At least one country must use imported inputs in its stage of the production process, and some of the resulting output must be exported.”

Mathematically, this can be expressed as:

$$\text{Equation 01-- } VS = A^M(I - A^D)^{-1}E$$

The VS chain clarifies each country's expertise at a particular stage in which intermediate resources imported from separate nations in the global value chain are used to create a degree of national export or connection with the global value chain. [Koopman et al.,2014](#) [12] expanding the idea of VS chain, the value of VS or imported contents in the export of the country consists of three elements: foreign value-added in final goods export, foreign value-added in intermediate goods export, and double-counted intermediate exports produced abroad. Figure 2 shows a case of a vertical specialized chain involving three countries. Country 1 produces intermediate goods and exports them to Country 2. Country 2 produces final goods (gross domestic product) by combining imported intermediate goods with capital and labour (added value) and domestically produced intermediate inputs. Finally, Country 2 exports some of its final products to Country 3. A key indicator of vertical specialization, called VS, captures Country 2's involvement in this process.

$$\text{Equation 02--} VS = \left(\frac{\text{imported intermediates}}{\text{gross output}} \right) \text{ exports}$$

$$\text{Equation 03--} VS = \left(\frac{\text{exports}}{\text{gross output}} \right) \text{ imported intermediates}$$

Figure 03. Vertical Specialization

Source: Adopted by [11]

In conclusion, the VS chain concept contributes to two main issues. First, the amount of world trade can be increased by following the concept of VS chains [13]. Second, higher levels of trade volume depend not only on traditional trade approaches that stimulate total exports but also on the concept of VS chains. However, the VS chain above has some weaknesses in that there is only one way to explain the country's participation in the global value chain by adopting intermediate use in the production of the country's exports.

The Leontief Decomposition

		Intermediate use		Final demand		Gross output
		Country A Industry	Country B Industry	Country A Industry	Country B Industry	
Country A	Industry	Intermediate use of domestic output	Intermediate use by B of exports from A	Final use of domestic output	Final use by B of exports from A	X_A
Country B	Industry	Intermediate use by A of exports from B	Intermediate use of domestic output	Final use by A of exports from B	Final use of domestic output	X_B
Value added		V_A	V_B			
Gross input		X_A	X_B			

Exports from A to B of intermediates
Exports from A to B of final products

Figure 04: Simple MRIO example

Source: Adopted by [14] and [15]

Figure 04, as expressed by Aslam et al. and Shepherd [14,15] depicts a simple example involving two countries and one industry. Intermediate use matrix elements that are perpendicular to the diagonal represent domestic use of domestically sourced intermediates, while elements that are off of the diagonal represent exports of those same intermediates. Just as with the demand matrix, the final use of domestic output is represented by the diagonal elements, while exports of goods and services are represented by the off-diagonal elements. Since it is summing elements across a row or a column, the total gross output for each country is obtained. Off-diagonal elements from the intermediate use matrix and the final demand matrix are summed to get the gross exports. It's a simple system. It's as follows:

$$\text{Equation 04} - AX + Y = X$$

It can represent the production system for G countries and N sectors with matrix algebra, using the row sum approach.

The input-output (A) and final demand (Y) product usage matrices are matrices with X (gross output) as their main ingredient. In the example above, it is obvious that AX is the intermediate use matrix.

Decomposition Analysis of Gross Export

At a nation exports goods and services to other countries, [Koopman et al.,2014 \[12\]](#) found that gross exports can be broken down into nine categories, and [Wang et al.,2018 \[17\]](#) (See Figure 3), repeating the same thing. Still, with a slight reordering (this can be divided down to eight categories): domestic value-added of direct exports of final goods, domestic value-added in intermediate exports absorbed by direct importers, domestic value-added in intermediate re-exports to a third country, domestic value-added in intermediate products returned through final imports, domestic value-added in intermediate products, which represents Income from intermediate imports, intermediate double-counting exports produced domestically, value-added abroad in exports of finished goods, value-added abroad in exports of intermediate goods, and double-counting exports of intermediate goods produced abroad [18,19]. The impact of a country's exports on economic growth cannot be directly measured using only gross exports because all eight categories of gross exports mentioned above play an essential role in economic growth. Besides, it will be compared with [Koopman et al., \(2014\) \[12\]](#) and definition of the terms of the [Wang et al., \(2018\) \[17\]](#) export decomposition equation [20]. The export decomposition accounting system defined by [Wang, Wei and Zhu \(2014\) \[21\]](#) is schematically depicted in Figure 2.7 [20]

According to [20] the first three categories - DVA_FIN, DVA_INT and DVA_INTrex - represent domestic value-added embedded in the gross exports of the economy, which is ultimately consumed abroad as end-use goods. The sum of three, named by [Wang et al., \(2018\) \[17\]](#) VAX_G, is the net measure of the economy's domestic value-added exports since it excludes any exported domestic value-added that goes back home. The fourth category, denoted RDV_B, is the domestic value-added built into the export of intermediate goods of the economy, which are first exported and returned for domestic consumption. The sum of VAX_G and RDV_B, presented as DVA, is the domestic value-added embedded in the gross exports of a sector of the economy, which includes the value-added created in all divisions of the economy that offer to the production of exports of that sector. In terms of the System of National Accounts, DVA is the GDP of the sector.

Figure 05: Conceptual Framework for Gross Trade Accounting

Source: Adopted from *Asian Development Bank, (2015) [20]* and *Wang et al., (2018) [17]*

According to *Asian Development Bank, (2015) [20]* the term DDC at the sectoral and bilateral levels covers the part of domestic value-added that is counted twice in the column elements of the corresponding diagonal block VBY. The added value is counted twice due to the two-way trade in intermediate products in the value chain. Therefore, the longer the global value chain and the more integrated the economy into the value chain at several levels, the greater the relative value of the DDC component in the exports of this sector. FVA_FIN and FVA_INT measure the foreign value-added invested in the export of commodities for final and intermediate use, respectively. In VBY, the sum of the columns of the corresponding off-diagonal block elements is the value-added abroad. The value-added of other economies embedded in the exports of a given economy that is double-counted in gross valuation for the same reason as DDC is defined by the term FDC or the foreign term double counting. For an economy well integrated into the global value chain, DDC and FDC increase as the frequency of bilateral trade increases. *Wang et al., (2018) [17]* classify these two components as pure double-counting terms or PDCs. As mentioned, the decomposition equation of *Wang et al., (2018) [17]* ultimately divide bilateral gross exports into different value-added and double-counting parts, depending on the territorial origin and destination of the added value. For any given sector, the sum of the components of the equation is precisely equal to the value of its gross exports, corresponding to the sum of the VBY column. The distinctive informational advantage of this expansion equation over the VBY matrix is its innate ability to isolate the

portions of value-added that are double-counted due to bilateral trade in intermediate products.

The sum of DDC, FVA_FIN, FVA_INT and FDC is an indicator for measuring the level of combination of the economy into the global value chain; Wang et al., (2018) [17] characterize it as an extension of the measure of vertical specialization (VS) proposed by Hwang et al., (2011) [13]. Each VS component is a characteristic cross-regional or cross-sectoral production sharing mechanism. When analyzed together, these four terms help define the position and contribution of a given sector of the economy to various global value chains.

This more detailed decomposition of gross exports is the defining contribution of Wang et al., (2018) [17] to the analysis of global value chains. Their decomposition equation shows that gross exports from economy (economy) to economy (r) at the sector level can be fully decomposed into the sum of 16 detailed terms in eight main categories. Economic interpretations of the terms of the equation are presented in Table 1. Another decomposition of gross exports is the defining contribution of Koopman, Wang and Wei (2014) [12], and the contribution of Wang et al., (2018) [17] were utterly equal. Anyone can get more information look at Wang et al., (2018) [17], Koopman et al., (2014) [12] and Asian Development Bank, (2015) [20]. Because achieving the objectives of this research proposal is not about the decomposition of gross exports.

Table 01 Compared with Koopman et al., (2014) [12] and Wang et al., (2018) [17]

Number		Label		Term		Math	Description
KWW	WWZ	KWW	WWZ	KWW	WWZ		
1	1	DV in direct final goods export	DVA_FIN	T1	T1	$(V^s B^{ss})^T \# Y^{sr}$	Domestic Value-Added exports in final goods exports
2	2	DV in intermediates exports absorbed by direct importers	DVA_INT	T2	T2	$(V^s L^{ss})^T \# (A^{sr} B^{rr} Y^{rr})$	Domestic Value Added in intermediate exports for production of all other countries' domestic used final goods. WWZ separates direct importer and third countries
2	3		DVA_INTrex1		T3	$(V^s L^{ss})^T \# (A^{sr} \sum_{t \neq s, r}^G B^{rt} Y^{tt})$	
3	3	DV in intermediates reexported in third countries IV	DVA_INTrex2	T3	T4	$(V^s L^{ss})^T \# (A^{sr} B^{rr} \sum_{t \neq s, r}^G Y^{tt})$	Domestic Value Added in intermediate exports used by producing final exports to the other countries. WWZ separates final exports from the direct importer and third countries.
3	3		DVA_INTrex3		T5	$(V^s L^{ss})^T \# (A^{sr} \sum_{t \neq s, r}^G B^{rt} \sum_{u \neq s, t}^G Y^{tu})$	
4	4	DV in intermediates that returns via final imports	RDV_FIN1	T4	T6	$(V^s L^{ss})^T \# (A^{sr} B^{rr} Y^{rs})$	Returned Domestic Value Added in final goods imports from the other countries. WWZ separates final imports from the direct importer and third countries.
4	4		RDV_FIN2		T7	$(V^s L^{ss})^T \# (A^{sr} \sum_{t \neq s, r}^G B^{rt} Y^{ts})$	
5	4	DV in intermediates that returns via intermediates imports.	RDV_INT	T5	T8	$(V^s L^{ss})^T \# (A^{sr} B^{rs} Y^{ss})$	Returned Domestic Value Added in intermediate imports
6	5	Double counted intermediate exports produced at home	DDC_FIN	T6	T9	$(V^s L^{ss})^T \# (A^{sr} B^{rs} \sum_{t \neq s}^G Y^{st})$	Double counted Domestic Value Added in gross exports. WWZ separates double counting due to final and intermediate exports production.
6	5		DDC_INT		T10	$(V^s L^{ss} \sum_{t \neq s}^G A^{st} B^{ts})^T \# (A^{rr} X^r)$	
7	6	FV in final goods exports	MVA_FIN	T7	T11	$(V^r B^{rs})^T \# Y^{sr}$	Foreign Value Added in exporting

7	6		OVA_FIN		T14	$(\sum_{t \neq s, r}^G V^t B^{ts})^T \# (A^{sr} L^{rr} Y^{rr})$	country's final goods exports. WWZ separates FVA from direct importer and from third countries.
8	7	FV in intermediate goods exports	MVA_INT	T8	T12	$(\sum_{t \neq s, r}^G V^t B^{ts})^T \# Y^{st}$	Foreign Value Added in exporting country's intermediate goods exports. WWZ separates FVA from direct importer and from third countries.
8	7		OVA_INT		T15	$(V^r B^{rs})^T \# (A^{sr} L^{rr} E^{r*})$	
9	8	Double counted intermediate exports produced abroad	MDC	T9	T13	$(V^r B^{rs})^T \# (A^{sr} L^{rr} Y^{rr})$	Double counted Foreign Value Added in exporting country's gross exports. WWZ separates FDC from direct importer and from third countries.
9	8		ODC		T16	$(\sum_{t \neq s, r}^G V^t B^{ts})^T \# (A^{sr} L^{rr} E^{r*})$	

Source: Author complied that with support from (12), (16) and (20)

Wang et al., (2018) [17] Notes:

$VAX_G = DVA_FIN + DVA_INT + DVA_INT_{rex}$, $FVA = FVA_FIN + FVA_INT$, $PDC = DDC + FDC$, $DVA_G = VAX_G + RDV_G$, $VS = FVA + PDC$; $MVA = \text{Term 11} + \text{Term 13}$, $OVA = \text{Term 12} + \text{Term 14}$, Total Value of Final exports = $DVA_FIN + FVA_FIN$, Total Value of intermediate exports = $DVA_INT + DVA_INT_{rex} + RDV_G + DDC + FVA_INT + FDC$.

Koopman et al., (2014) [12] Notes: (i) Value-added exports by a country equals (1) + (2) + (3); (ii) GDP in exports equals (1) + (2) + (3) + (4) + (5); (iii) Domestic content in a country's exports equals (1) + (2) + (3) + (4) + (5) + (6); (iv) (7) + (8) + (9) is labeled as VS, and (3) + (4) + (5) + (6) is part of VS1 labeled by HIY (2001); (v) (4) is also labeled as VS1* by Daudin, Riffart, and Schweisguth (2011); (vi) (4) through (9) involve value added that crosses national borders at least twice, and are the sources of multiple counting in official trade statistics

Upstreamness and Average Production Length¹

The upstreamness and average production length can be measured for product efficiency. In position in GVCs the economy has been measured through the upstreamness Index, by [Antràs & Chor, 2013.](#), [Fally, 2012](#) and [Wang et al., 2017](#) [23–25]. The upstreamness Index is the average distance from the end-use of a sector. A new sector is described by [Miller & Temurshoev \(2017\)](#) [26] whose output is absorbed as the final use in the economy in several stages. According to [Bank \(2020\)](#) [27] explained the share of the overall output in an economic sector which is sold to end consumers also refers to a simpler measure of upstreamness. This is said to be a relatively upstream industry in which the economic sector sells a large amount of its output for medium use, i.e. a lower ratio between final use and total output.

The backward average length of the production of a particular sector economy based on retroactive industrial links is the ratio of total inputs induced from the country sector to the value of the final goods and services produced in this sector economy, which induced these inputs describe that [Wang et al., 2017](#) [24]. The average production length indicates the number of upstream processes in the economy, i.e. the relative downstreamness economic or economic sector before the final product is realized.

In a given industry-based economy, the forward average production length is defined [24] as the ratio of total gross yields in all economic products to the value-added in a given sector-based economy that induces these gross yields. The average production length based on industrial connection transmission measures the number of downstream processes which is considered gross output by an economic sector. This measure therefore also provides an economic or economic sector with its relative upstreaming.

Revealed comparative advantage (RCA) and New Revealed comparative advantage (NRCA)²

The most exciting factor for quantifying the impact and benefits of the global value chain, as shown in the traditional equation, is the Revealed Comparative Advantage Index (RCA). The traditional RCA is a measure of the comparative advantage of a particular sector of a country in the global economy.

As defined by the [Nam et al., \(2002\)](#) [28]: *The RCA index is defined as the ratio of two shares. The numerator is the share of a country's total exports of the commodity of interest in its total exports. The denominator is share of world exports of the same commodity in total world exports.*

Also accepts a value from 0 to $+\infty$. A country is considered to have a revealed comparative advantage if the value is greater than one (28). However, there is a limitation. The index is influenced by anything that distorts the structure of trade, such as trade barriers.

According to [Sessomboon, \(2015\)](#) [19] and [Asian Development Bank, \(2015\)](#) [20] found out [Wang et al., \(2018\)](#) [17] and [Koopman et al., \(2014\)](#) [12] proposed a new method for measuring comparative advantage called New Revealed Comparative Advantage (NRCA). This NRCA can be calculated using the same formula as

¹ Appendix 01: Technical Note

² Appendix 01: Technical Note

RCA, but the variable needs to be changed from gross exports to domestic value added in gross exports, which is the sum of the first to fifth terms or the equivalent of the sum of the first fourth terms in the equation. The reason to consider using NRCA in the model instead of regular RCA is that NRCA omits foreign value-added and net double counting in gross exports, which is an amount from (T6 [12]) to (T9 [12]) in table 1. Neither do these two terms reflect the potential for competition in the global value chain.

Methodology

There is only one method of gathering data sources and two ways of delivering information. This research uses an analysis of the Asian Development Bank MIRO database to present descriptive information about the industries³. The period of time it covers is 2000, 2007 to 2019. Econometric analysis is another. A total of 455 observations were recorded over a time span of 13 years (2007 to 2019), with one dependent variable⁴ and 08 explanatory variables (a total of observations = 455, N = 35, and Time = 13).

The Econometrics Analysis [30] has 04 models: They are,

$$\begin{aligned} \ln SGOW_1 &= \alpha + \beta_1 \ln EX + \beta_2 \ln GVCF + \beta_3 \ln GVCB + \beta_4 \ln K + \beta_5 \ln L + \varepsilon \\ \ln SGOW_2 &= \alpha + \beta_1 \ln DVA + \beta_2 \ln GVCF + \beta_3 \ln GVCB + \beta_4 \ln K + \beta_5 \ln L + \varepsilon \\ \ln SGOW_3 &= \alpha + \beta_1 \ln FVA + \beta_2 \ln GVCF + \beta_3 \ln GVCB + \beta_4 \ln K + \beta_5 \ln L + \varepsilon \\ \ln SGOW_4 &= \alpha + \beta_1 \ln PDC + \beta_2 \ln GVCF + \beta_3 \ln GVCB + \beta_4 \ln K + \beta_5 \ln L + \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

The panel data used in the research paper was utilized in two separate models, which included fixed and random effects. Therefore, one model was derived from two.

FINDING AND ANALYSIS

The data collected to learn results from this study are examined in this section. Firstly, the decomposition of Sri Lankan industries' gross export is examined. Second, a comparison is provided for the conventional revealed comparative advantage (RCA) index for Sri Lankan industries with the new revealed comparative advantage (NRCA). Third, the upstreamness and average length of Sri Lankan production sectors will be discussed in order to improve production efficiency. Next, the impact of the global value chain on the export-led growth strategy is investigated by the Sri Lankan economic sector. The impact of the determinants on Sri Lankan exports is also studied.

Decomposition of Sri Lankan Industries' Gross Export

The Figure⁵ shows Sri Lankan's annual gross export and domestic value added from 2000 and 2007 to 2019 in five sectors. The value of Gross Export's main sector in the year 2000 has reached US\$1856,145, million. In addition, that might happen with the added value of domestic value, which is \$1502,313 million in 2000. There were also relatively low other sectors. Gross export value of 1518,801 US\$ million for personal and public

³ Appendix 02: Sector Aggregation used in Input Output Table

⁴ Appendix 03: Key Variables

⁵ Appendix 04: Gross Export and Domestic Value Added of Sri Lankan in 2000, 2007 to 2019

services became the second largest sector in 2000. In addition, this may be worth added to the domestic value, which is worth \$1289.99 million in 2000. However, Gross Export's Medium to high technology manufacturing value of US\$ 40.62 million was reduced in 2000, from five sectors. This might be added to the Domestic Value, which was the status of US \$ million in 2000 in 23.09. Prior to 2000, therefore, the Primary sector handled Sri Lankan exports.

The Gross export's low technology manufactured value was small and relatively low in 2000, but the value of Gross export on low-technology production increased multiple times while the value of other sector industries rose in 2007 to 2019 period. This led to growth from \$3547.03 million in gross exports to \$6790.08 million in 2007 and 2018 for the manufacture of low technology. In addition, the value added to the Domestic Value could have increased, with low-technology production becoming key sector from 2794.38 USD million to 5745.47 in 2007 and 2018. In 2007-2019, primary sectors were being secondary transformed into sectors that reported that the Gross Export value was US\$2773.98 million in 2007 and 2018 was US\$6589.69 million. This could also be added to the Domestic Value, which is 2007 amounted to US\$2365.45 million and 2018 amounted to US\$ 5745.47 million. The value of the Gross Export business services, however, was US\$ 57.88 million, which became a small (out of 5 sectors in 2007). Sri Lanka was enormously lost in export income. Because Business services were third out of five in 2000. But Business Services gradually came up and reported that 493.43 million US dollars were in 2018 and 418.31 million US dollars in 2019. Therefore, the Low-technology manufacturing sector is the main export sector in Sri Lanka. Further, this is a turning point for, Sri Lankan Economy in the last decade because Sri Lanka is going forward from Primary to Low technology.

The Figure⁶ illustrates Sri Lankan's annual gross export and foreign value added from 2000 and 2007 to 2019 in five sectors. Also, as above indicated Gross Export value same here in this figure. Furthermore, the Primary Sector's foreign value-added is US\$289.74 million in 2000. Other sectors were also relatively low. Personal and public services, with a foreign value-added of 175.29 US\$ million, became the second largest sector in 2000. However, low-tech manufacturing has a value of US\$ 63.75 million, and medium to high-tech manufacturing has a value of US\$ 14.17 million, making it a small sector out of five. Next, Foreign value added increased, with low-technology production becoming a key sector from 635.60 USD million to 896.86 in 2007 and 2018. In 2007-2019, primary sectors were being secondary transformed into sectors that reported that the foreign value-added was US\$322.90 million in 2007 and 2018 was US\$543.85 million. The foreign value-added business services, however, was US\$ 9.64 million, which became small like previously (out of 5 sectors in 2007). Moreover, the foreign value added of business services was US\$ 46.75 million in 2018 and US\$ 35.98 million in 2019.

The Figure⁷ explains Sri Lankan's annual gross export and pure double counted in Gross Export from 2000 and 2007 to 2019 in five sectors. Also, as above⁶ (Appendix 4) appeared Gross Export value same here in this figure.

⁶ Appendix 04: Gross Export and Domestic Value Added of Sri Lankan in 2000, 2007 to 2019

⁷ Appendix 05: Gross Export and Foreign Value Added of Sri Lankan in 2000, 2007 to 2019

In addition, that, pure double counted⁸ in Gross Export in two decades maintain greater than 90 percent of Sri Lankan exports. Furthermore, the Primary Sector's pure double counted is US\$64.08 million in 2000. Other sectors were also relatively small figures. Personal and public services, with a foreign value-added of 53.51 US\$ million, became the second largest sector in 2000. However, low-tech manufacturing has a value of US\$ 8.79 million, and medium to high-tech manufacturing has a value of US\$ 3.34 million, making it a small sector out of five. Next, Foreign value added increased, with low-technology production becoming a key sector from 117.05 USD million to 147.74 in 2007 and 2018. In 2007-2019, primary sectors were being secondary transformed into sectors that reported that the foreign value-added was US\$85.63 million in 2007 and 2018 was US\$157.81 million. The foreign value-added business services, however, was US\$ 1.85 million, which became small like previously (out of 5 sectors in 2007). Moreover, the pure double counted in Gross Export of business services was US\$ 8.45 million in 2018 and US\$ 6.48 million in 2019.

However, when it comes to Foreign Value Added and Pure Double Counted, it may be impossible to draw any conclusions about the five sectors because they are divided into 15 or 35 sectors, respectively.

Table 02: Domestic Value – Added, Foreign Value – Added and Pure Double Counted (% Gross Export) of Sri Lankan in 2000 and 2010

Year	15 Sector - Industries	DVA%	FVA%	PDC%
2000	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	83%	14%	4%
	Mining and quarrying	71%	26%	3%
	Light manufacturing	95%	5%	0%
	Heavy manufacturing	91%	6%	3%
	Utilities	56%	36%	8%
	Construction	78%	19%	3%
	Trade services	73%	23%	3%
	Hotels and restaurants	90%	7%	3%
	Transport services	80%	17%	2%
	Telecommunications	97%	3%	0%
	Financial intermediation	82%	14%	5%
	Real estate, renting, and business activities	64%	28%	8%
	Public administration and defense	94%	4%	2%
	Education, health, and social work	70%	25%	5%
	Other personal services	73%	21%	6%
2010	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	88%	9%	3%
	Mining and quarrying	86%	12%	2%
	Light manufacturing	97%	3%	0%

⁸ Appendix 06: Pure Double Counted (% Gross Export) of Sri Lankan in 2000, 2007 to 2019

Heavy manufacturing	95%	3%	2%
Utilities	57%	33%	10%
Construction	89%	9%	2%
Trade services	78%	19%	3%
Hotels and restaurants	93%	6%	1%
Transport services	90%	8%	2%
Telecommunications	0%	0%	0%
Financial intermediation	91%	6%	3%
Real estate, renting, and business activities	75%	19%	6%
Public administration and defense	95%	3%	2%
Education, health, and social work	79%	17%	3%
Other personal services	83%	7%	10%

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on [Koopman et al., \(2014\)](#) and [Sessomboon, \(2015b\)](#) [12,18,19]

Table 03: Domestic Value – Added, Foreign Value – Added and Pure Double Counted (% Gross Export) of Sri Lankan in 2018 and 2019

Year	15 Sector - Industries	DVA%	FVA%	PDC%
2018	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	89%	9%	2%
	Mining and quarrying	83%	15%	3%
	Light manufacturing	99%	0%	0%
	Heavy manufacturing	95%	3%	2%
	Utilities	50%	39%	11%
	Construction	90%	9%	1%
	Trade services	85%	13%	2%
	Hotels and restaurants	94%	5%	1%
	Transport services	90%	9%	2%
	Telecommunications	98%	2%	0%
	Financial intermediation	89%	8%	3%
	Real estate, renting, and business activities	75%	18%	7%
	Public administration and defense	95%	3%	2%
	Education, health, and social work	85%	12%	3%
	Other personal services	84%	10%	6%
2019	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	90%	8%	2%
	Mining and quarrying	84%	14%	2%
	Light manufacturing	100%	0%	0%
	Heavy manufacturing	95%	3%	2%
	Utilities	51%	37%	13%
	Construction	90%	9%	1%
	Trade services	86%	13%	2%
	Hotels and restaurants	94%	4%	1%

Transport services	91%	8%	1%
Telecommunications	99%	1%	0%
Financial intermediation	90%	8%	2%
Real estate, renting, and business activities	76%	17%	6%
Public administration and defense	96%	3%	2%
Education, health, and social work	86%	12%	2%
Other personal services	85%	9%	6%

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on Koopman et al., (2014) and Sessomboon, (2015b) [12,18,19]

The Table 02 and 03 presents Domestic Value – Added, Foreign Value – Added and Pure Double Counted (% Gross Export) of Sri Lankan in 2000, 2010, 2018 and 2019. In 2000, Light manufacturing (95%), Heavy manufacturing (91%), Hotels and restaurants (90%) and Public administration and defense (94%) were more than 90% percent domestic value added and which were goods exports products in Sri Lanka. But Mining and quarrying (71%), Utilities (56%), Trade services (73%), Real estate, renting, and business activities (64%), Education, health, and social work (70%) and Other personal services (73%) are less than 75% percent domestic value added which encouraged Foreign Value – Added and Pure Double Counted in export. In 2000, Utilities showed 36% of Foreign Value – Added and 8% Pure Double Counted in export indicating highest share of them. Compare in 2000, in 2019 only Utilities was displayed 51% of Domestic Value – Added, 37% of Foreign Value – Added and 13% of Pure Double Counted in exports and all other sectors were more than 80% percent indicating that Sri Lanka is good position in current environment. However, Sri Lanka is labour fulfilled country but capital or technology, research and development level is low level. According to table 04 shows that average of Gross Export, Domestic Value – Added, Foreign Value – Added and Pure Double Counted of Sri Lankan in 2007 to 2019 which capital usage were less than 1% present in export. Example: Manufacturing, nec; recycling (0.14%), Chemicals and chemical products (0.08%), Transport equipment (0.17%), Coke, refined petroleum, and nuclear fuel (0.83%) etc.

Table 04: Average of Gross Export, Domestic Value – Added, Foreign Value – Added and Pure Double Counted of Sri Lankan in 2007 to 2019

35 Sector - Industries	EX%	DVA%	FVA%	PDC%
1. Public administration and defense, compulsory social security	23.96%	22.66%	33.56%	18.50%
2. Electrical and optical equipment	15.35%	15.48%	14.35%	16.02%
3. Other nonmetallic minerals	14.74%	15.46%	11.42%	8.18%
4. Other community, social, and personal services	11.79%	13.22%	3.06%	9.49%
5. Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	4.09%	4.30%	2.92%	3.24%
6. Real estate activities	3.65%	3.57%	3.44%	7.24%
7. Machinery, nec	3.18%	3.38%	2.27%	1.29%

8. Sale, maintenance, and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles; retail sale of fuel	2.93%	3.09%	2.11%	1.78%
9. Financial intermediation	2.43%	2.70%	0.92%	1.21%
10. Mining and quarrying	1.98%	1.53%	4.70%	2.99%
11. Leather, leather products, and footwear	1.90%	1.06%	5.36%	11.50%
12. Electricity, gas, and water supply	1.77%	1.72%	2.28%	0.99%
13. Post and telecommunications	1.71%	1.80%	1.03%	2.36%
14. Rubber and plastics	1.50%	1.68%	0.44%	1.12%
15. Hotels and restaurants	1.41%	1.23%	2.15%	3.56%
16. Construction	1.18%	1.31%	0.49%	0.58%
17. Air transport	0.94%	0.83%	1.39%	2.05%
18. Wood and products of wood and cork	0.84%	0.82%	0.94%	0.81%
19. Coke, refined petroleum, and nuclear fuel	0.83%	0.65%	1.87%	1.40%
20. Textiles and textile products	0.70%	0.62%	0.89%	2.17%
21. Wholesale trade and commission trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	0.52%	0.49%	0.74%	0.48%
22. Education	0.44%	0.34%	1.05%	0.71%
23. Private households with employed persons	0.42%	0.42%	0.41%	0.29%
24. Food, beverages, and tobacco	0.37%	0.24%	1.13%	0.89%
25. Renting of M&Eq and other business activities	0.27%	0.30%	0.08%	0.20%
26. Water transport	0.26%	0.30%	0.07%	0.00%
27. Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles; repair of household goods	0.24%	0.23%	0.25%	0.45%
28. Transport equipment	0.17%	0.17%	0.21%	0.04%
29. Manufacturing, nec; recycling	0.14%	0.11%	0.35%	0.11%
30. Other supporting and auxiliary transport activities; activities of travel agencies	0.09%	0.10%	0.03%	0.01%
31. Chemicals and chemical products	0.08%	0.08%	0.07%	0.32%
32. Pulp, paper, paper products, printing, and publishing	0.07%	0.08%	0.01%	0.00%
33. Basic metals and fabricated metal	0.03%	0.03%	0.02%	0.00%
34. Health and social work	0.01%	0.01%	0.00%	0.01%
35. Inland transport	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on [Koopman et al., \(2014\)](#) and [Sessomboon, \(2015b\)](#) [12,18,19]

Therefore, Sri Lanka is good for primary and Low technology manufacturing but there is no strategic plan for future to becoming more comparative nation in world. Furthermore, primary, and Low technology manufacturing earn money, less than other sectors but it gives less capital, or technology, research and development and greater than labour like Sri Lanka.

Conventional Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) and New Revealed Comparative Advantage (NRCA) Index

According to Table 05 compares 5 Sectors Traditional Revealed Comparative Advantage (TRCA) and New Revealed Comparative Advantage (NRCA) Index in Sri Lankan Industries in 2000,2007 to 2019. In the initial position, the comparative advantage was reduced in terms of the changeover from TRCA to NRCA in 2000, 2007, and 2019.

Table 05: Compare 5 sectors TRCA and NRCA in Sri Lankan Industries in 2000,2007 to 2019

Year	Sector	NRCA	TRCA	Status
2000	Primary	5.191757	8.681794	Decrease
	Low-technology manufacturing	0.887323	1.059932	Decrease
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.031628	0.023945	Increase
	Business services	2.354289	3.945886	Decrease
	Personal and public services	5.394525	10.38373	Decrease
2007	Primary	1.749942	1.821823	Decrease
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.680899	3.945614	Decrease
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.600974	0.44828	Increase
	Business services	1.843236	3.214115	Decrease
	Personal and public services	0.868966	0.448012	Decrease
2008	Primary	1.799546	1.920448	Decrease
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.541461	3.779176	Decrease
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.573192	0.394425	Increase
	Business services	1.894478	3.167874	Decrease
	Personal and public services	0.969006	0.573113	Increase
2009	Primary	1.711161	1.563337	Increase
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.320748	3.927289	Decrease
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.568839	0.474901	Increase
	Business services	1.776051	3.580976	Decrease
	Personal and public services	1.468486	2.047668	Decrease
2010	Primary	1.804509	1.21083	Increase
	Low-technology manufacturing	4.45785	4.878448	Decrease
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.490091	0.369349	Decrease
	Business services	1.818405	2.65475	Decrease
	Personal and public services	0.494664	0.012504	Increase
2011	Primary	1.856087	1.390898	Increase
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.947269	3.282776	Increase
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.30498	0.315458	Decrease
	Business services	2.037777	3.288811	Decrease
	Personal and public services	1.367459	1.94384	Decrease

	Primary	1.680998	1.382043	Increase
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.85141	3.139573	Increase
2012	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.43895	0.484346	Decrease
	Business services	2.36849	3.550619	Decrease
	Personal and public services	1.543049	1.979304	Decrease
	Primary	1.603462	1.317159	Increase
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.805034	3.043597	Increase
2013	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.515632	0.440915	Increase
	Business services	2.281494	3.410635	Decrease
	Personal and public services	2.098454	3.246611	Decrease
	Primary	1.345457	1.407979	Decrease
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.635601	2.801015	Increase
2014	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.373829	0.25941	Increase
	Business services	2.538146	4.406982	Decrease
	Personal and public services	1.322843	2.027771	Decrease
	Primary	1.528775	1.51941	Increase
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.715994	2.930339	Increase
2015	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.295111	0.226945	Increase
	Business services	2.451348	4.107514	Decrease
	Personal and public services	1.250309	1.79414	Decrease
	Primary	1.358236	1.362276	Decrease
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.233951	2.513139	Increase
2016	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.220819	0.214299	Increase
	Business services	2.563958	4.26595	Decrease
	Personal and public services	1.259492	1.745352	Decrease
	Primary	1.366366	1.339879	Increase
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.399177	2.717307	Increase
2017	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.202134	0.19024	Increase
	Business services	2.356505	3.814932	Decrease
	Personal and public services	1.30948	1.792858	Decrease
	Primary	1.356978	1.267576	Increase
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.274254	2.627809	Increase
2018	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.281872	0.286183	Decrease
	Business services	2.487073	3.858269	Decrease
	Personal and public services	1.285476	1.764919	Decrease
	Primary	1.153856	1.123246	Increase
2019	Low-technology manufacturing	3.260829	2.607688	Increase
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	0.246917	0.344863	Decrease

Business services	2.531086	3.856432	Decrease
Personal and public services	1.461225	1.79724	Decrease

Source: Author complied using ADB MIRO and calculation based on Koopman et al., (2014) and Sessomboon, (2015b) [12,18,19]

These Sectors were in 2000, 2007 and 2008 all other Sectors except Medium- to high-technology manufacturing, In 2009, all other sectors except Primary and Medium- to high-technology manufacturing sectors, in 2010 all other sectors except Primary and Personal and public services , in 2011 , 2012 , 2018 and 2019 all other sectors except primary and Low-technology manufacturing, in 2013, 2015 and 2017 Business services and Personal and public services in 2014 and 2016 all sectors except Low-technology manufacturing and Medium- to high-technology manufacturing. Therefore, it can be reapplied above conclusion.

According to the Figure 06 / Table 06 Textiles and textile products ⁹ was ranked number eleven in 2000 was shifted Number one in 2010 and 2019. In 2019, Inland transport, Food, beverages, and tobacco, Other community, social, and personal services, Hotels and restaurants, Rubber and plastics, Wholesale trade and commission trade, Air transport, Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing and Health and social work were ranked up to ten. Moreover, in 2000, Textiles and textile products was ranked 11, Rubber and plastics was ranked 23 and Air transport was ranked 17 also, in 2010 Other community, social, and personal services was ranked 14, Hotels and restaurants was ranked 29, Air transport was ranked 12 and Health and social work was ranked 31 all these industries have promoted in 2019 top ten list.

⁹ Appendix 07 and Appendix 08

Figure 06: Compare Ranking of Sectoral NRCA in 2000, 2010 and 2019

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on Koopman et al., (2014) and Baris & Lumba, (2020) [12,31]

Table 06: Compare Ranking of Sectoral NRCA in 2000, 2010 and 2019

Sector	2000	2010	2019
Textiles and textile products	11	1	1
Inland transport	3	3	2
Food, beverages, and tobacco	8	2	3
Other community, social, and personal services	1	14	4
Hotels and restaurants	5	29	5
Rubber and plastics	23	5	6
Wholesale trade and commission trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	4	7	7
Air transport	17	12	8
Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	2	6	9
Health and social work	7	31	10
Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles; repair of household goods	25	13	11
Financial intermediation	12	11	12
Wood and products of wood and cork	18	10	13

Post and telecommunications	13	9	14
Other nonmetallic minerals	24	15	15
Construction	9	8	16
Manufacturing, nec; recycling	16	4	17
Sale, maintenance, and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles; retail sale of fuel	33	19	18
Electricity, gas, and water supply	14	17	19
Real estate activities	10	23	20
Pulp, paper, paper products, printing, and publishing	22	18	21
Chemicals and chemical products	28	21	22
Leather, leather products, and footwear	27	20	23
Renting of M&Eq and other business activities	15	24	24
Coke, refined petroleum, and nuclear fuel	20	16	25
Mining and quarrying	6	28	26
Public administration and defense; compulsory social security	19	32	27
Other supporting and auxiliary transport activities; activities of travel agencies	32	25	28
Basic metals and fabricated metal	31	27	29
Education	21	33	30
Electrical and optical equipment	30	26	31
Transport equipment	29	22	32
Machinery, nec	26	30	33
Water transport	34	34	34
Private households with employed persons	35	35	35

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on Koopman et al., (2014) and Baris & Lumba, (2020) [12,31]

Upstreamness and Average Length of Sri Lankan Production Sectors

Table 07 illustrates Upstreamness and Average Length of Sri Lankan Production for 5 Sectors in Sri Lanka. According to table, in 2000 minimum sector in upstreamness was Low-technology manufacturing sectors (1.164¹⁰) and maximum sector was Medium- to high-technology manufacturing (2.123) in Sri Lanka. Along with that in 2000 minimum sector in backward measures of average production length was Medium- to high-technology manufacturing (3.405) and maximum sector was Personal and public services (3.782) in Sri Lanka. Moreover, minimum sector in Forward measures of average production length was Primary sectors (3.033) and maximum sector was Low-technology manufacturing (3.758) in Sri Lanka.

Table 07: Upstreamness and Average Length of Sri Lankan Production 5 - Sectors

Year	Sector	PLvGVC	PLyGVC	Upstreamness
2000	Primary	3.03399126	3.71924212	1.58998526
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.7582413	3.53742263	1.164665272
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	3.23732409	3.40567805	2.123371927
	Business services	3.46496752	3.64268319	1.859193542
	Personal and public services	3.431721	3.78271063	1.476456667
2010	Primary	3.80998146	4.10496688	1.864423305
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.23321216	4.121035	1.443603815
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	3.81638796	3.90364415	2.079643688

¹⁰ Appendix 09 and Appendix 10

	Business services	3.77048626	4.01628654	1.718194023
	Personal and public services	4.66517609	4.13133056	1.19291774
2018	Primary	3.62426055	4.20831479	2.108226834
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.59700749	4.10941299	2.157877995
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	3.96113998	3.84603024	2.072287203
	Business services	3.72268007	4.34645563	2.504216711
	Personal and public services	4.08601201	4.37795026	0
2019	Primary	3.5206006	4.19367231	2.605747161
	Low-technology manufacturing	3.57477535	4.09630329	2.424494439
	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing	3.84848087	3.82639144	1.763879388
	Business services	3.74526993	4.29450781	1.70387405
	Personal and public services	4.20872457	4.30026272	2.097491815

Source: Author complied using ADB MIRO and calculation based on Wang et al., (2017) and Baris & Lumba, (2020) [21,31]

According to above table 07, in 2019 minimum sector in upstreamness was Business service sector (1.703) and maximum sector was Primary sectors (2.605) in Sri Lanka. Further, in 2019 minimum sector in backward measures of average production length was Medium- to high-technology manufacturing (3.826) and maximum sector was Personal and public services (4.300) in Sri Lanka. Moreover, minimum sector in Forward measures of average production length was Primary sectors (3.033) and maximum sector was Personal and public services (4.208) in Sri Lanka.

The Impact of the Global Value Chain on the Sectoral Changes in Sri Lanka

The panel regression outcome is revealed in Table 08, which includes eight models engaged in the regression:¹¹

Table 08: Result from Panel Regression

Variables	Model 01	Model 02	Model 03	Model 04
lnEX	-0.0212** (0.00880)	-0.00622 (0.0112)		
lnDVA			-0.0204** (0.00880)	-0.00644 (0.0112)
lnFVA				
lnPDC				
lnGVCF	0.146*** (0.0459)	-0.104** (0.0431)	0.146*** (0.0459)	-0.103** (0.0431)
lnGVCB	-0.136* (0.0723)	-0.308*** (0.0745)	-0.136* (0.0724)	-0.309*** (0.0746)
lnK	0.127*** (0.0191)	0.107*** (0.0179)	0.126*** (0.0191)	0.107*** (0.0179)
lnL	0.188*** (0.0248)	0.459*** (0.0262)	0.188*** (0.0248)	0.457*** (0.0262)
Constant	-5.912*** (0.246)	-8.558*** (0.229)	-5.923*** (0.245)	-8.545*** (0.229)
Observations	316	316	316	316
Number of Sector	32	32	32	32
R-squared	0.6053	0.8783	0.6082	0.8781
F / Wald Statistics	23.06	439.16	22.95	434.42

¹¹ Appendix 11: Descriptive Statistics

Prob F / Wald	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Hausman Test	648.67		654.42	
Prob Hausman Test	0.000		0.000	
Sector FE	Yes	No	Yes	No
Year FE	Yes	No	Yes	No

Note: Standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author calculated using ADB MIRO

The Models 01 and 02 will explain the influence of the Export, Model 03 and 04 will clarify the stimulus of the Domestic Value Added, Model 05 and 06 will explain the effect of the Foreign Value Added, and Model 07 and 08 will clarify the stimulus of the Pure Double Counted.

As a result of the Hausman test, all the fixed effect models (Model 01, Model 03, Model 05 and Model 07) became successful panel regressions. In case of Model 01, it is accepted the alternatives hypotheses at the 5% level of significance that all coefficients are equal to zero. Therefore, Model 01 is statistically accepted which have R-squared 60.53% of the variation in the Sectoral Changes in Sri Lanka on Export, GVCF, GVCB, K and L variables. Then in Model 01 show that the export has a negative impact on Sectoral share (-0.0212) in Sri Lanka. Next in the GVCF has a positive impact on Sectoral share (0.146) but GVCB has a negative impact on Sectoral share (-.136) in Sri Lanka. Furthermore, Capital (0.127) and Labour (0.188) have positive impact on Sectoral share in Sri Lanka.

In case of Model 03, it is accepted the alternatives hypotheses at the 5% level of significance that all coefficients are equal to zero. Therefore, Model 03 is statistically accepted which have R-squared 60.82% of the variation in the Sectoral Changes in Sri Lanka on DVA, GVCF, GVCB, K and L variables. Then in Model 03 show that the DVA has a negative impact on Sectoral share (-0.0212) in Sri Lanka. Next in the GVC-Forward has a positive impact on Sectoral share (0.146) but GVC-Backward has a negative impact on Sectoral share (-.136) in Sri Lanka. Furthermore, Capital (0.126) and Labour (0.188) have positive impact on Sectoral share in Sri Lanka.

Continued to Table 08

Variables	Model 05	Model 06	Model 07	Model 08
lnEX				
lnDVA				
lnFVA	-0.0186** (0.00879)	0.00272 (0.0109)		
lnPDC			-0.00738** (0.00302)	-0.00321 (0.00411)
lnGVCF	0.148*** (0.0462)	-0.105** (0.0430)	0.144*** (0.0458)	-0.105** (0.0431)
lnGVCB	-0.135* (0.0725)	-0.306*** (0.0743)	-0.147** (0.0722)	-0.310*** (0.0745)
lnK	0.124*** (0.0190)	0.106*** (0.0177)	0.126*** (0.0190)	0.108*** (0.0179)
lnL	0.187*** (0.0249)	0.463*** (0.0261)	0.187*** (0.0248)	0.461*** (0.0261)

Constant	-5.942*** (0.244)	-8.615*** (0.225)	-6.021*** (0.243)	-8.606*** (0.227)
Observations	316	316	316	316
Number of Sector	32	32	32	32
R-squared	0.6007	0.8805	0.6108	0.8779
F / Wald Statistics	22.70	451.95	23.10	445.00
Prob F / Wald	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Hausman Test	588.20		607.52	
Prob Hausman Test	0.000		0.000	
Sector FE	Yes	No	Yes	No
Year FE	Yes	No	Yes	No

Note: Standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Source: Author calculated using ADB MIRO

In case of Model 05, it is accepted the alternatives hypotheses at the 5% level of significance that all coefficients are equal to zero. Therefore, Model 05 is statistically accepted which have R-squared 60.07% of the variation in the Sectoral Changes in Sri Lanka on FVA, GVCF, GVCB, K and L variables. Then in Model 05 show that the export has a negative impact on Sectoral share (-0.0186) in Sri Lanka. Next in the GVC-Forward has a positive impact on Sectoral share (0.148) but GVC-Backward has a negative impact on Sectoral share (-.135) in Sri Lanka. Furthermore, Capital (0.124) and Labour (0.187) have positive impact on Sectoral share in Sri Lanka.

In case of Model 07, it is accepted the alternatives hypotheses at the 5% level of significance that all coefficients are equal to zero. Therefore, Model 07 is statistically accepted which have R-squared 61.08% of the variation in the Sectoral Changes in Sri Lanka on PDC, GVCF, GVCB, K and L variables. Then in Model 07 show that the export has a negative impact on Sectoral share (-0.00738) in Sri Lanka. Next in the GVC-Forward has a positive impact on Sectoral share (0.144) but GVC-Backward has a negative impact on Sectoral share (-.147) in Sri Lanka. Furthermore, Capital (0.126) and Labour (0.187) have positive impact on Sectoral share in Sri Lanka.

Conclusion

The Main objective of this paper was to examine to measure decomposition analysis of impact of the Global Value Chain's on Sri Lankan Economy. Any country of the export sector is affected by Domestic Value-Added (DVA), Foreign Value-Added (FVA), and Pure Double Counted (PDC), Traditional Revealed Comparative Advantage (TRCA), New Revealed Comparative Advantage (NRCA) indexes, Average production length of GVCs based on forward linkages (PLvGVC), Average production length of GVCs based on backward linkages (PLyGVC), Upstreamness, GVC participation based on forward linkages (GVCF), GVC participation based on backward linkages (GVCB), Labour Productivity (L) and Capital Efficiency (K). The paper reached the conclusion based on variables and models.

First, examine to measure decomposition analysis of impact of the Global Value Chain's on Sri Lankan Economy revealed the following conclusion. Primary Sectors have shifted to low-technology manufacturing in domestic value-added (DVA) since 2007, as compared to 2000. Further, this is a turning point for, Sri Lankan Economy in the last decade because Sri Lanka is going forward from Primary to Low technology. Furthermore, primary, and Low technology manufacturing earn money, less than other sectors but it gives less capital, or technology, research and development and greater than labour like Sri Lanka. All these implies that medium to high-technology manufacturing must become the number one sector in the future, with more export income earned through the global value chain (GVC). Because, according to 2019 figures, it has 282.06 million US dollars in domestic value-added (DVA). Exports and Foreign Direct Investment must materialize infrastructure facilities in order for Sri Lankan policymakers to achieve this.

Second, comparison between Traditional Revealed Comparative Advantage (TRCA) and New Revealed Comparative Advantage (NRCA) indexes. As above mentioned, Primary Sectors have shifted to low-technology manufacturing in New Revealed Comparative Advantage (NRCA) index in 2019, as compared to 2000. It implies that medium to high-technology manufacturing must become the number one sector in the future, with more export income earned through the global value chain (GVC). Because, according to 2019 figures, it has 0.246 in New Revealed Comparative Advantage (NRCA) index but 0.344 in Traditional Revealed Comparative Advantage (TRCA).

Third, to assess the upstreamness and average production length of Sri Lankan sectors to improve production efficiency. In 2000, low-technology manufacturing has the upstreamness 1.16412 value which lowest value in Sri Lanka. In 2019, Business Services got the upstreamness 1.70313 which lowest value in Sri Lanka. The sub-objective was met, but questions about production and supply arose. This is because it is that supply for low-tech products should be represented in 2019, but the manufacturing sector represents business services.

The research results confirmed that, as expected, there was a negative correlation between export and sectoral present share in Sri Lanka, meaning that increasing exports results in a decline in Sectoral percentage share. Also, Domestic Value Added (DVA), Foreign Value Added (FVA), and Pure Double Counted (PDC) in exports were all other main variables affected. Thus, all other variables indicate a positive relationship between sectoral present share in Sri Lanka and strong statistical significance, but there is no relationship between sectoral present share in Sri Lanka and GVCB and L, which show the opposite direction. Exposing these facts all confirms that Sri Lanka's Primary and Low Technology Manufacturing governance of export is controlled by Secondary and Low Technology Manufacturing; and GVC participation according to backward linkages (GVCB) and Labour Productivity (L) essential for each sector, since GVC participation according to forward

12 In 2000, PLvGVC had a low-tech product value of 3.758, which was the highest in Sri Lanka and PLvGVC had Primary Sector a 3.719 which was the highest in Sri Lanka.

13 In 2019, PLYGVC had a Personal and public services value of 4.208, which was the highest in Sri Lanka and the same sector PLvGVC had a value of 4.300 which was the highest in Sri Lanka.

linkages (GVCF) is also supported by an increase in customer base and an increase in capital efficiency. In order to encourage meet the requirements of the global value chain, Sri Lanka must have the ability to provide medium to high-technology manufacturing in the world.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 01: Technical Note

Upstreamness Index:

Fally (2012) and Antràs & Chor (2013) [23,25] developed a measure of distance of a production sector from final demand called *upstreamness*. Succinctly, the *upstreamness* of sector r in economy i , or U_{ri} , is the average distance from final use and is given by:

$$U_i^r = 1 \times \frac{F_i^r}{X_i^r} + 2 \times \frac{\sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{j=1}^J a_{ij}^{rs} F_j^s}{X_i^r} + 3 \times \frac{\sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{t=1}^S \sum_{k=1}^J a_{ij}^{rs} a_{jk}^{st} F_k^t}{X_i^r} + \dots$$

where F is final demand, X is gross output, superscripts refer to sector, and subscripts refer to in economy. Moreover, a_{ij}^{rs} is the dollar amount of sector r 's output from economy i needed to produce a dollar's worth of sector s 's output in economy j .

Backward measures of average production length:[24]

Taking all economy-sector pairs (s,i) where final goods and services which induced the intermediate inputs in economy-sector (r,j) , the average production length in the economy based on backward industrial linkage is given by:

$$PL_y = 1 \frac{VBB\hat{Y}}{V\hat{B}Y}$$

where V is the value-added coefficient matrix vector, B is the Leontief inverse matrix, and \hat{Y} is the diagonal matrix of final demands.

Forward measures of average production length: [24]

Taking all economy-sector pairs (s,i) where the value added originated and all economy-sector pairs (r,j) where the value-added is counted as gross output, the average production length in the economy based on forward industrial linkage is given:

$$PL_v = 1 \frac{\hat{V}BBY}{\hat{V}BY}$$

where \hat{V} is the diagonal matrix of value-added coefficient vector V , B is the Leontief inverse matrix, Y is the final demand vector, and X is the output vector.

Traditional revealed comparative advantage [32]

Measures the relative advantage or disadvantage of a country-sector as “revealed” by trade patterns. Traditional revealed comparative advantage (TRCA) of economy r is defined as

$$TRCA_i^t = \frac{\frac{e_i^{r^*}}{\sum_i^n e_i^{r^*}}}{\frac{\sum_t^G e_i^{r^*}}{\sum_i^n \sum_t^G e_i^{r^*}}}$$

That is, the TRCA is equal to the export share of an industry to the total exports of an economy divided by the export share of this industry in the world.

An RCA value of less than 1 implies that the economy is not specialized in exports of this industry. Similarly, an RCA value exceeding 1 implies that the economy is specialized in this industry's exports.

New revealed comparative advantage [17]

Wang, Wei, and Zhu (2013) [17] proposed a new measure of revealed comparative advantage (NRCA) that excludes foreign value-added and pure double-counted terms in gross exports, but includes indirect exports of an economy-sector's value-added through other sectors of the exporting economy. The authors defined NRCA as the share of an economy-sector's forward-linkage-based measure of domestic value-added in exports, $dvix_f$, in the economy's total domestic value-added in exports relative to the sector's total forward-linkage-based domestic value-added in exports from all economies as a share of global value-added in exports.

The NRCA is defined as:

$$NRCA_i^t = \frac{\frac{dvix_f_i^{r^*}}{\sum_{i=1}^n dvix_f_i^{r^*}}}{\frac{\sum_t^G dvix_f_i^{r^*}}{\sum_i^n \sum_t^G dvix_f_i^{r^*}}}$$

NRCA uses the same interpretation as TRCA, except that, instead of using gross exports, e , NRCA only includes the domestic value-added component of export in each sector.

Appendix 02: Sector Aggregation used in Input-Output Tables

Code	35-sector aggregation	Code	15-sector aggregation
1	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	1	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing
2	Mining and quarrying	2	Mining and quarrying
3	Food, beverages, and tobacco	3	Light manufacturing
4	Textiles and textile products	4	Heavy manufacturing
5	Leather, leather products, and footwear	5	Utilities
6	Wood and products of wood and cork	6	Construction
7	Pulp, paper, paper products, printing, and publishing	7	Trade services
8	Coke, refined petroleum, and nuclear fuel	8	Hotels and restaurants
9	Chemicals and chemical products	9	Transport services
10	Rubber and plastics	10	Telecommunications
11	Other nonmetallic minerals	11	Financial intermediation
12	Basic metals and fabricated metal	12	Real estate, renting, and business activities
13	Machinery, nec	13	Public administration and defense
14	Electrical and optical equipment	14	Education, health, and social work
15	Transport equipment	15	Other personal services
16	Manufacturing, nec; recycling		
17	Electricity, gas, and water supply		
18	Construction		
19	Sale, maintenance, and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles; retail sale of fuel	Code	5-sector aggregation
20	Wholesale trade and commission trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1	Primary
21	Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles; repair of household goods	2	Low-technology manufacturing
22	Hotels and restaurants	3	Medium- to high-technology manufacturing
23	Inland transport	4	Business services
24	Water transport	5	Personal and public services
25	Air transport		
26	Other supporting and auxiliary transport activities; activities of travel agencies		
27	Post and telecommunications		
28	Financial intermediation		
29	Real estate activities		
30	Renting of M&Eq and other business activities		
31	Public administration and defense; compulsory social security		
32	Education		
33	Health and social work		
34	Other community, social, and personal services		
35	Private households with employed persons		

Source: Author compiled using [Bank, \(2020\) \[27\]](#)

Appendix 03: Key Variables

Variable	Variables in Details	Framework used
Sector	Sector - 5 Sectors, 15 Sectors and 35 Sectors	Bank, A. D. 2020. Economic Indicators for South and Central Asia: Input–Output Tables. In Asian Development Bank (ADB) (Issue December).
SGOW	Sectoral Percentage Share	P. Antràs, D. Chor, T. Fally, and R. Hillberry. 2012. Measuring the Upstreamness of Production and Trade Flows. <i>American Economic Review</i> . 102 (3). pp. 412–416.
EX	Export	Sessomboon, P. 2015. Decomposition Analysis of Global Value Chain’S Impact on Thai Economy. In Thammasat University.
DVA	Domestic Value-Added	Sessomboon, P. 2015. Decomposition Analysis of Global Value Chain’S Impact on Thai Economy. In Thammasat University.
FVA	Foreign Value-Added	Sessomboon, P. 2015. Decomposition Analysis of Global Value Chain’S Impact on Thai Economy. In Thammasat University.
PDC	Pure Double Counted	Sessomboon, P. 2015. Decomposition Analysis of Global Value Chain’S Impact on Thai Economy. In Thammasat University.
GVCF	GVC participation based on forward linkages	Wang, Z., S. Wei, X. Yu, and K. Zhu. 2017. Measures of Participation in Global Value Chains and Global Business Cycles. <i>NBER Working Paper</i> No. 23222. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.
GVCB	GVC participation based on backward linkages	Wang, Z., S. Wei, X. Yu, and K. Zhu. 2017. Measures of Participation in Global Value Chains and Global Business Cycles. <i>NBER Working Paper</i> No. 23222. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.
PLVGVC	Average production length of GVCs based on forward linkages	Wang, Z., S. Wei, X. Yu, and K. Zhu. 2017. Characterizing Global Value Chains: Production Length and Upstreamness. <i>NBER Working Paper</i> No. 23261. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.
PIYGVC	Average production length of GVCs based on backward linkages	Wang, Z., S. Wei, X. Yu, and K. Zhu. 2017. Characterizing Global Value Chains: Production Length and Upstreamness. <i>NBER Working Paper</i> No. 23261. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.

Upstreamness	Upstreamness	Antràs, P. and D. Chor. 2018. On the Measurement of Upstreamness and Downstreamness in Global Value Chains. <i>NBER Working Paper</i> No. 24185. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.
NRCA	NRCA	Z. Wang, S. Wei, and K. Zhu. 2018. Quantifying International Production Sharing at the Bilateral and Sector Levels. <i>NBER Working Paper</i> No. 19677. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.
TRCA	TRCA	B. Balassa. 1965. Trade Liberalisation and "Revealed" Comparative Advantage. <i>The Manchester School</i> . 33(2) pp. 99-123.
K	Capital Efficiency	P. Antràs, D. Chor, T. Fally, and R. Hillberry. 2012. Measuring the Upstreamness of Production and Trade Flows. <i>American Economic Review</i> . 102 (3). pp. 412–416.
L	Labour Productivity	P. Antràs, D. Chor, T. Fally, and R. Hillberry. 2012. Measuring the Upstreamness of Production and Trade Flows. <i>American Economic Review</i> . 102 (3). pp. 412–416.

Source: Author compiled using Bank (2020), Antràs et al. (2012) , Sessomboon (2015), Wang et al., (2017b), Wang et al., (2017a), Antràs & Chor (2018), Wang et al., (2018a) ,and Balassa (1965)

Appendix 04: Gross Export and Domestic Value – Added of Sri Lankan in 2000, 2007-2019

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on [Koopman et al., \(2014\)](#) and [Sessomboon, \(2015b\)](#) [12,18,19]

Appendix 05: Gross Export and Foreign Value – Added of Sri Lankan in 2000, 2007-2019

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on [Koopman et al., \(2014\)](#) and [Sessomboon, \(2015b\)](#) [12,18,19]

Appendix 06: Pure Double Counted (% Gross Export) of Sri Lankan in 2000, 2007-2019

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on [Koopman et al., \(2014\)](#) and [Sessomboon, \(2015b\)](#) [12,18,19]

Appendix 07: Compare 15 sectors TRCA and NRCA in Sri Lankan Industries in 2000,2010, 2018 to 2019

Year	Sector	NRCA	TRCA	Status
2000	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	6.186724	10.53738	Decrease
	Mining and quarrying	1.414562	1.637433	Decrease
	Light manufacturing	0.75328	0.435501	Decrease
	Heavy manufacturing	0.026811	0.019864	Increase
	Utilities	0.387582	0.022892	Increase
	Construction	0.936418	1.195066	Decrease
	Trade services	1.971702	2.456895	Decrease
	Hotels and restaurants	1.820278	2.746631	Decrease
	Transport services	4.181774	8.123015	Decrease
	Telecommunications	0.409265	1.204428	Decrease
	Financial intermediation	0.483309	0.302232	Increase
	Real estate, renting, and business activities	0.645842	0.209625	Increase
	Public administration and defense	0.055363	0.077999	Decrease
	Education, health, and social work	0.669884	0.145455	Increase
	Other personal services	8.304858	16.29204	Decrease
2010	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	2.161579	1.45527	Increase
	Mining and quarrying	0.107228	0.04892	Decrease
	Light manufacturing	5.351484	4.429902	Increase
	Heavy manufacturing	0.363886	0.288213	Increase
	Utilities	0.594783	0.003144	Increase
	Construction	1.617908	5.96617	Decrease
	Trade services	1.303209	1.475104	Decrease
	Hotels and restaurants	0.093285	0.018274	Increase
	Transport services	3.599666	5.752542	Decrease
	Telecommunications	1.140342	4.971814	Decrease
	Financial intermediation	0.897025	0.128136	Increase
	Real estate, renting, and business activities	0.243345	0.117601	Increase
	Public administration and defense	0.018567	0	Increase
	Education, health, and social work	0.029654	8.72E-14	Increase
	Other personal services	0.800682	0.020623	Increase
2018	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	1.71628	1.593977	Increase
	Mining and quarrying	0.137478	0.159742	Decrease
	Light manufacturing	4.620874	3.641893	Increase
	Heavy manufacturing	0.128636	0.140459	Decrease
	Utilities	0.485892	0.016939	Decrease
	Construction	0.499921	0.602187	Decrease
	Trade services	1.354708	1.903917	Decrease
	Hotels and restaurants	1.851479	3.20063	Decrease
	Transport services	5.128021	8.38605	Decrease
	Telecommunications	0.674275	1.710012	Decrease
	Financial intermediation	0.934404	0.601347	Increase
	Real estate, renting, and business activities	0.271317	0.107862	Increase
	Public administration and defense	0.067855	0.094409	Decrease
	Education, health, and social work	0.450078	0.05991	Increase
	Other personal services	1.93641	2.794403	Decrease
2019	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	1.482808	1.4323	Increase

Mining and quarrying	0.132407	0.163587	Decrease
Light manufacturing	4.618273	3.627571	Increase
Heavy manufacturing	0.141871	0.271246	Decrease
Utilities	0.499404	0.01759	Increase
Construction	0.514397	0.609643	Decrease
Trade services	1.360662	1.909912	Increase
Hotels and restaurants	1.803299	3.171918	Decrease
Transport services	5.271148	8.479857	Decrease
Telecommunications	0.761666	1.828345	Decrease
Financial intermediation	0.989889	0.609016	Decrease
Real estate, renting, and business activities	0.318076	0.106546	Increase
Public administration and defense	0.110225	0.086144	Increase
Education, health, and social work	0.742279	0.06708	Increase
Other personal services	2.106487	2.835416	Decrease

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on [Koopman et al., \(2014\)](#) and [Sessomboon, \(2015b\)](#) [12,18,19]

Appendix 08: Compare 35 sectors TRCA and NRCA average in Sri Lankan Industries in 2007 to 2019

	Sector	NRCA	TRCA	Status
1	Textiles and textile products	8.98109	7.53958	Increase
2	Food, beverages, and tobacco	4.73688	3.2823	Increase
3	Inland transport	4.61135	7.80285	Decrease
4	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	1.9256	1.76741	Increase
5	Other community, social, and personal services	1.83289	2.33268	Decrease
6	Rubber and plastics	1.7644	1.95956	Decrease
7	Wholesale trade and commission trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1.70855	1.86503	Decrease
8	Air transport	1.51429	1.66829	Decrease
9	Hotels and restaurants	1.4597	2.53209	Decrease
10	Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles; repair of household goods	1.22194	2.58836	Decrease
11	Manufacturing, nec; recycling	1.13361	0.8613	Decrease
12	Health and social work	0.90077	0.18492	Increase
13	Financial intermediation	0.85557	0.43946	Increase
14	Construction	0.80751	2.16724	Decrease
15	Wood and products of wood and cork	0.80007	0.74161	Decrease
16	Post and telecommunications	0.71559	2.23289	Decrease
17	Other nonmetallic minerals	0.61641	0.56865	Increase
18	Electricity, gas, and water supply	0.51298	0.14602	Increase
19	Coke, refined petroleum, and nuclear fuel	0.48494	0.49053	Decrease
20	Leather, leather products, and footwear	0.45473	0.26303	Increase
21	Sale, maintenance, and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles; retail sale of fuel	0.45197	0.90693	Decrease
22	Pulp, paper, paper products, printing, and publishing	0.44195	0.52566	Decrease
23	Real estate activities	0.34386	0.64218	Decrease
24	Public administration and defense; compulsory social security	0.3299	0.67784	Decrease
25	Chemicals and chemical products	0.28296	0.10636	Decrease
26	Other supporting and auxiliary transport activities; activities of travel agencies	0.23654	0.28318	Decrease
27	Renting of M&Eq and other business activities	0.18435	0.26124	Decrease
28	Mining and quarrying	0.16601	0.14393	Increase
29	Education	0.15852	0.29487	Decrease
30	Electrical and optical equipment	0.10311	0.06957	Increase
31	Basic metals and fabricated metal	0.09048	0.05668	Increase
32	Transport equipment	0.07837	0.05703	Increase
33	Machinery, nec	0.02777	0.02738	Increase
34	Water transport	0.00975	0.00465	Increase
35	Private households with employed persons	0	0	None

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on [Koopman et al., \(2014\)](#) and [Sessomboon, \(2015b\)](#) [12,18,19]

Appendix 09: Upstreamness and Average Length of Sri Lankan Production 15 - Sectors

Year	Sector	PLvGVC	PlyGVC	Upstreamness
2000	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	2.904160952	3.688293559	1.367292881
	Mining and quarrying	3.526866586	3.836732295	2.435393279
	Light manufacturing	3.137571781	3.388351616	1.915601182
	Heavy manufacturing	3.269133113	3.497315151	2.139502607
	Utilities	4.475462596	3.782532791	1.93798929
	Construction	3.742047865	3.525718666	1.041596532
	Trade services	3.357472901	3.650900323	2.276402401
	Hotels and restaurants	3.306659756	3.75661088	1.423554478
	Transport services	3.188430958	3.578008961	1.694040806
	Telecommunications	3.557951919	3.608725713	1.97279076
	Financial intermediation	3.880055126	3.831045393	2.051203508
	Real estate, renting, and business activities	3.985199571	3.632661591	1.619587897
	Public administration and defense	4.176049874	3.627791666	1.024708116
	Education, health, and social work	3.653875869	3.953641971	1.090056603
Other personal services	3.13943766	3.787103632	1.719230591	
2010	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	3.742400343	4.106699086	1.792568668
	Mining and quarrying	4.131219369	4.096733076	2.205974806
	Light manufacturing	3.245560961	4.081732366	1.543479773
	Heavy manufacturing	3.782309464	3.857247754	2.172700564
	Utilities	4.56127909	4.018879611	2.400329215
	Construction	3.126583131	4.225442898	1.089210757
	Trade services	3.538034811	4.217793108	1.811207094
	Hotels and restaurants	4.570805207	4.273597284	1.158766001
	Transport services	3.320743411	3.913667048	1.587956939
	Telecommunications	3.416878324	3.905871436	2.203935828
	Financial intermediation	4.275242629	3.762214287	2.016217598
	Real estate, renting, and business activities	4.572380343	4.037231795	1.682034516
	Public administration and defense	4.635833601	3.978250098	1.024508782
	Education, health, and social work	4.968961635	3.96382297	1.025391416
Other personal services	4.590227411	4.234802229	1.302022662	
2018	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	3.622091338	4.151048492	2.572624623
	Mining and quarrying	3.631623023	4.402681474	1.005854402
	Light manufacturing	3.33644323	4.094750523	1.045497588
	Heavy manufacturing	3.975703231	3.861100383	1.087148151
	Utilities	4.625083468	4.291985497	1.436525242
	Construction	4.038796037	4.060329744	1.019090472
	Trade services	3.535903507	4.338988162	1.972056359
	Hotels and restaurants	3.334793294	4.266167674	3.158216073
	Transport services	3.412757652	4.30075533	1.38427792
	Telecommunications	3.790366326	4.144475686	1.395551011
	Financial intermediation	3.985421367	4.603769278	1.269850729
	Real estate, renting, and business activities	4.588714743	4.352292687	2.564161156
	Public administration and defense	4.504430627	4.170098839	2.405946866
	Education, health, and social work	4.32684002	4.34372461	2.658815014
Other personal services	3.873616533	4.462609277	2.144052502	
2019	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	3.529195245	4.139689345	2.019752937

Mining and quarrying	3.493912845	4.361298001	2.590712366
Light manufacturing	3.276606873	4.085009743	2.356400188
Heavy manufacturing	3.841907651	3.827873816	2.120749219
Utilities	4.608626037	4.266298236	1.899950547
Construction	4.072721804	4.048538325	1.912954895
Trade services	3.553153249	4.270525303	1.897163408
Hotels and restaurants	3.337153354	4.24867659	2.273012861
Transport services	3.411262506	4.267725094	1.100177113
Telecommunications	3.824043442	4.103531375	1.019439283
Financial intermediation	4.002991378	4.521195688	1.002608514
Real estate, renting, and business activities	4.642241814	4.292026854	2.092218689
Public administration and defense	4.774188035	4.01873768	0
Education, health, and social work	4.466409327	4.193787258	2.220085875
Other personal services	3.950302251	4.423041471	2.210872437

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on Wang et al., (2017) and Baris & Lumba, (2020) [21,31]

Appendix 10 : Upstreamness and Average Length of Sri Lankan Production 35 - Sectors

	35 Sectors	PLvGVC	PlyGVC	Upstreamness
1	Private households with employed persons	0	0	0.86114239
2	Education	4.117472	4.510124	1.373230745
3	Public administration and defense; compulsory social security	4.329518	4.171679	1.478873577
4	Construction	3.75881	4.048073	1.5320739
5	Hotels and restaurants	3.622158	4.281354	1.585441981
6	Real estate activities	4.865092	4.298031	1.595525865
7	Air transport	2.732781	3.82328	1.609345453
8	Health and social work	4.688783	4.138998	1.662210763
9	Leather, leather products, and footwear	3.685181	4.408692	1.693708854
10	Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles; repair of household goods	3.59238	4.216078	1.713155959
11	Transport equipment	3.381416	4.084694	1.714640412
12	Machinery, nec	3.804392	4.094004	1.747488132
13	Agriculture, hunting, forestry, and fishing	3.696449	4.202054	1.807515707
14	Other community, social, and personal services	4.034593	4.399387	1.860625574
15	Wood and products of wood and cork	3.594764	4.042257	1.905713475
16	Financial intermediation	4.080092	4.311091	1.914391492
17	Food, beverages, and tobacco	3.121681	4.055802	1.91593737
18	Other nonmetallic minerals	4.033343	3.866368	1.92983984
19	Textiles and textile products	3.322821	4.338396	1.93716715
20	Inland transport	3.443489	4.217493	1.938680722
21	Basic metals and fabricated metal	4.144255	4.074201	1.942880935
22	Manufacturing, nec; recycling	3.718534	4.161444	1.943109934
23	Electrical and optical equipment	3.959864	4.058676	1.976370058
24	Post and telecommunications	3.702256	4.060188	2.021369839
25	Water transport	3.718095	4.479188	2.02673571
26	Sale, maintenance, and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles; retail sale of fuel	3.653648	4.243001	2.100874904

27	Rubber and plastics Average	3.329016	4.088071	2.130753845
28	Other supporting and auxiliary transport activities; activities of travel agencies	4.17868	4.428005	2.217853988
29	Mining and quarrying	3.84467	4.352973	2.230491043
30	Renting of M&Eq and other business activities	3.952115	4.287356	2.275808045
31	Wholesale trade and commission trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	3.487385	4.264965	2.281584869
32	Coke, refined petroleum, and nuclear fuel	3.955322	3.703491	2.311230777
33	Electricity, gas, and water supply	4.615773	4.25603	2.378357173
34	Chemicals and chemical products	4.136566	4.135872	2.502663931
35	Pulp, paper, paper products, printing, and publishing	4.048435	4.137659	2.683871942

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO and calculation based on Wang et al., (2017) and Baris & Lumba, (2020) [21,31]

Appendix 11: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	N	MEAN	SD	MIN	MAX
lnSGOW	408	-4.496	1.731	-9.853	-2.075
lnEX	404	4.039	2.968	-26.28	8.153
lnDVA	404	3.820	2.951	-26.31	7.965
lnPDC	404	-0.182	6.062	-92.71	4.463
lnGVCF	408	-3.057	1.568	-8.795	-0.951
lnGVCB	408	-2.050	0.919	-5.665	-0.369
lnK	362	3.467	2.991	-5.707	9.222
lnL	377	6.303	2.034	-3.419	9.067

Source: Author compiled using ADB MIRO

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